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Research Article

**ANALYSIS OF ROLE OF NFKBIA PROMOTER
POLYMORPHISMS CONTRIBUTE TO A DECREASED RISK
OF OVARIAN CANCER****Dr Tauqeer Ahmed¹, Dr Orooj Asif², Dr Arooj Fatima³**¹Basic Health Unit Lodhray, Sialkot²Basic Health Unit Birri Shah Rahman, Gujranwala³District Head Quarter Teaching hospital, Gujranwala**Abstract:**

Introduction: Ovarian cancer is one of the leading forms of cancer, in worldwide. Each year, there is an estimated 225,500 new incidences of ovarian cancer cases globally. The lack of effective screening methods causes >70% of ovarian cancer patients to be diagnosed at late stages, which leads to the low 5-year survival rate and high mortality rate of the disease. Objectives of the study: The basic objective of the study is to find the NFKBIA promoter polymorphisms which contribute towards the decreased risk of ovarian cancer in females. Materials and methods: The whole experimental work was conducted in Allama Iqbal Memorial Teaching hospital, Sialkot during February 2018 till October 2018. All experiment is done according to the rules and regulations of authority. The genomic DNA obtained was then used in polymerase chain reaction (PCR). Result: The association of the inflammatory gene polymorphisms with ovarian cancer risk was measured in OR units, with the wild type genotype served as the reference. Conclusion: It is concluded that there is no association found in NFKBIA genetic polymorphism and ovarian cancer in local population of Pakistan.

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INTRODUCTION:

Ovarian cancer is one of the leading forms of cancer, in worldwide. Each year, there is an estimated 225,500 new incidences of ovarian cancer cases globally. The lack of effective screening methods causes >70% of ovarian cancer patients to be diagnosed at late stages, which leads to the low 5-year survival rate and high mortality rate of the disease¹. Worldwide, ovarian cancer contributes to 114,000 deaths annually. A method for the identification of individuals at a higher risk of the cancer is therefore necessary for improving ovarian cancer screening strategy².

The principal risk factors for the occurrence of ovarian cancer are germ line mutations in the *BRCA1* or *BRCA2* genes. However, the carriers of such mutations account for only a small portion of total ovarian cancer cases, and a substantial proportion of ovarian cancer risk among sporadic cases remained unexplained³. It has been suggested that common low penetrance genetic variations could confer moderate risk to ovarian cancer cases without a heritable basis. Single nucleotide polymorphisms of genes involved in cancer-related pathways represent the candidates of such genetic variations⁴.

Cancer cells are characterized by the attainment of several characteristics that enable them to become tumorigenic¹. Cancer is a group of diseases characterized by uncontrolled growth and spread of abnormal cells⁵. If the spread is not controlled, it can result in death. Cancer is initiated by both external factors (tobacco, infectious organisms, chemicals, and radiation) and internal factors (inherited mutations, hormones, immune conditions, and mutations that occur from metabolism). These contributory factors

may act collectively or in sequence to initiate or promote carcinogenesis⁶.

Objectives of the study

The basic objective of the study is to find the NFKB1A promoter polymorphisms which contribute towards the decreased risk of ovarian cancer in females.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

The whole experimental work was conducted in the Allama Iqbal Memorial Teaching hospital, Sialkot during February 2018 till October 2018. All experiment is done according to the rules and regulations of authority. For this study we select the 20 female patients who was suffering from ovarian cancer. The blood was drawn for further analysis of micronutrients. Genomic DNA was extracted from the blood samples obtained using Blood Genomic DNA Kit according to the manufacturer's protocol. The genomic DNA obtained was then used in polymerase chain reaction (PCR).

Statistical analysis

Student's t-test was performed to evaluate the differences in roughness between group P and S. Two-way ANOVA was performed to study the contributions. A chi-square test was used to examine the difference in the distribution of the fracture modes (SPSS 19.0 for Windows, SPSS Inc., USA).

RESULT:

The association of the inflammatory gene polymorphisms with ovarian cancer risk was measured in OR units, with the wild type genotype served as the reference. The risk association was summarized in table 01. There is no significant risk association was observed for the GC genotype of the NFKB1A polymorphism.

Table 01: Analysis of risk association of the polymorphisms with ovarian cancer.

Genotype	Patients	Controls	OR (95% CI)	p
PPARG				
Pro/Pro	624	643	Reference	—
Pro/Ala	62	42	1.52 (1.01–2.29)	0.04
Ala/Ala	1	2	0.52 (0.05–5.70)	0.59
IL6				
GG	683	676	Reference	—
GC	4	11	0.36 (0.11–1.14)	0.08
CC	0	0	—	—
E-selectin				
AA	662	644	Reference	—
AC	25	43	1.77 (1.07–2.93)	0.03
CC	0	0	—	—
NFKB1				
Del/Del	221	253	Reference	—
Del/Ins	351	339	1.19 (0.94–1.50)	0.15

Ins/Ins	115	95	1.39 (1.00–1.92)	0.05
NFKB1A				
CC	486	478	Reference	—
CT	181	190	0.94 (0.74–1.19)	0.59
TT	20	19	1.04 (0.55–1.96)	0.92
ICAM-1				
KK	209	180	Reference	—
KE	322	362	0.77 (0.60–0.98)	0.04
EE	156	145	0.93 (0.69–1.25)	0.62

DISCUSSION:

Important intracellular signal transduction pathways that are necessary for the action of some antineoplastic agents can also be affected by oxidative stress. There are two major pathways of drug-induced apoptosis following cellular damage by anti-neoplastic agents: (1) The mitochondrial pathway, initiated by release of cytochrome c; and (2) the CD95 death receptor pathway, initiated by CD95L binding to its death receptor⁸.

Unlike several other Asian countries, ovarian cancer is the most common cancer of gynecologic origin in Pakistani women. This study is probably the first detailed account of clinico-pathologic features of these patients. Such information is rarely forthcoming from other developing countries making it difficult to compare the results⁹.

The link between inflammation and cancer development has been well established.⁶ However, studies investigating the relationship between inflammatory gene polymorphisms and cancer risk have generated contradictory findings¹⁰. The allelic distributions of various polymorphisms could vary geographically and ethnically, thus leading to the discordant findings between these polymorphisms and cancer risk. In this study, we reported the association between six inflammatory gene polymorphisms and ovarian cancer risk in a Chinese population. Our analysis showed that three of the polymorphisms were associated with an increased ovarian cancer risk, and one polymorphism was associated with a decreased ovarian cancer risk¹⁰.

CONCLUSION:

It is concluded that there is no association found in NFKB1A genetic polymorphism and ovarian cancer in local population of Pakistan.

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